

Synthesis and Desulphurisation of Substituted 12*H*-[1]-Benzopyrano[3,4-*b*][1,4]benzothiazin-6-ones

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Nine substituted 12*H*-[1]-benzopyrano[3,4-*b*][1,4]benzothiazin-6-ones have been prepared by condensation of the corresponding 4-hydroxycoumarins with 2-aminothiophenol in dimethyl sulphoxide and one of these subjected to desulphurisation reaction with Raney nickel forming 4-anilino-coumarin. Their spectral properties and physiological activity have been evaluated.

THE condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarin with 2-aminothiophenol has been shown to result in the formation of 12*H*-[1]-benzopyrano[3,4-*b*][1,4]benzothiazin-6-one¹.

The synthesis of benzopyranobenzothiazines with different substituents in the benzene ring of coumarin moiety have been undertaken and reported in the present investigation. In addition to the synthesis, a new investigation, namely Raney nickel desulphurisation of 12*H*-[1]-benzopyrano[3,4-*b*][1,4]benzothiazin-6-one, has been carried out and the compound formed is characterised as 4-anilino-coumarin on the basis of spectral data and its synthesis.

As a representative case, 7-methyl-4-hydroxycoumarin in molar proportion was stirred with 2-aminothiophenol in dry dimethyl sulphoxide at 140-145° for 1.5 h. Under these conditions, dehydration and oxidative cyclisation took place with the formation of orange crystals of 3-methyl-12*H*-[1]-benzopyrano[3,4-*b*][1,4]benzothiazin-6-one (1). The compound was insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution indicating that the 4-hydroxy group of coumarin is not free. Elemental analysis indicated the presence of nitrogen and sulphur.

Chart 1

Adopting this procedure, 2-methyl-, 5-methyl-, 2-chloro-, 4-chloro-, 2-chloro-3-methyl-, 2,4-dichloro-, 2-bromo-, 3,4-benzo-12*H*-[1]-benzopyrano[3,4-*b*][1,4]benzothiazin-6-ones compounds have been synthesised.

All these compounds exhibited uv absorption maxima at 268 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.4 to 4.6) assignable to C_6H_5-NH chromophore, at 310 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.7 to 4.2) assignable to cinnamoyl chromophore and at 408 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 2.5 to 3.2) assignable to $HN-C_6H_4-S$ chromophore (Table 1). Ir spectra showed two bands at 3350 (NH) and 1700 cm^{-1} (coumarin $C=O$).

The nmr spectrum of 3-methylbenzopyranobenzothiazin-6-one (in $DMSO-D_6$) indicated signal at δ 2.3 (3H, s, Me), 8.85 (1H, s, NH) exchangeable with D_2O , 7.8 (1H, s, C_1-H) and 7.2-6.95 (6H, m, ArH). Mass spectrum of the compound showed presence of parent ion M^+ at m/z 281, $p+1$ (18%) and $p+2$ (9%) peaks supporting the presence of one sulphur atom in the molecule. Fragmentation pattern seems to follow four different pathways. In one pathway, M^+ fragments to give rise to m/z 158 (coumarin moiety) and 123 (2-amino thiophenol moiety). A loss of CO from M^+ gives rise to an ion at m/z 253 which subsequently fragments to form 106 and 147 (benzothiazine moiety). M^* ion fragments to an ion at m/z 193 supported by M^+ 135 as a result of loss of CO_2 and CS. The base peak at m/z 163 has been assigned to a structure as shown in the fragmentation chart (Chart 2).

The above compound was treated with acetic anhydride and a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid to form a colourless crystalline acetate, ν_{max} 1720 (coumarin $C=O$) and 1640 cm^{-1} (NAC).

12*H*-3-Methyl-[1]-benzopyrano[3,4-*b*][1,4]benzothiazin-6-one was subjected to Raney nickel desulphurisation reaction in ethanol. A colourless compound was formed (tlc single spot on silica gel G, with benzene and ethyl acetate 1:1, insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution). The elemental analysis indicated the presence of nitrogen and absence of sulphur, ν_{max} 1700 (coumarin $C=O$) and 3330 cm^{-1} (NH); δ (in $DMSO-D_6$), 2.3 (s, Me), 5.5 (1H, s, 3H- in coumarin moiety), 7.4-7.8 (8H, m,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 12H-[1]-BENZOPYRANO[3,4-b][1,4]BENZOTHAZIN-6-ONES

Sl. no.	Substituent	M.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			U _v λ _{max} MeOH nm	log ε	I _r ν _{max} (cm ⁻¹)	
				C	H	N			N-H	C=O
1.	3-Methyl	308	82	68.28 (68.32)	3.87 (3.91)	4.88 (4.92)	268 310 408	4.5 4.1 2.8	3330	1700
2.	2-Methyl	285	82	68.27 (68.32)	3.86 (3.91)	4.87 (4.92)	266 310 410	4.6 3.7 2.8	3335	1700
3.	4-Methyl	328	82	68.27 (68.32)	3.26 (3.91)	4.86 (4.92)	270 310 408	4.5 4.4 2.8	3340	1700
4.	4-Chloro	302	80	59.74 (59.80)	2.60 (2.65)	4.60 (4.65)	262 310 406	4.5 3.8 3.0	3320	1700
5.	2-Chloro	315	80	59.76 (59.80)	2.60 (2.65)	4.60 (4.65)	268 310 408	4.5 3.8 2.8	3314	1705
6.	2,4-Dichloro	348	80	58.52 (58.57)	2.02 (2.08)	4.11 (4.16)	268 310 408	4.5 4.2 3.0	3310	1700
7.	2-Chloro-3-methyl	345	83	60.90 (60.95)	3.12 (3.17)	4.40 (4.44)	268 310 410	4.6 4.2 3.6	3340	1700
8.	2-Bromo	292	81	52.11 (52.17)	2.08 (2.02)	4.0 (4.05)	270 315 406	4.6 3.8 2.5	3315	1705
9.	3,4-Benzo	>350	68	71.86 (71.92)	3.41 (3.47)	4.88 (4.42)	268 310 408	4.5 4.1 2.8	3330	1700
10.	Unsubstituted	386	82	67.96 (67.41)	3.82 (3.97)	5.20 (5.24)	264 310 408	4.4 4.0 2.9	3310	1700

Chart 2

ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, NH) was further found exchangeable with D₂O.

Chart 3

On the basis of the above spectral data the compound has been assigned to 7-methyl-4-anilino coumarin (2)

structure. This compound was prepared by a known procedure^{2,3} and found identical with the above product of desulphurisation in all respects (m.m.p. undepressed, ir superimposable).

All the compounds have been tested for antibacterial and antifungal activity and found active. The antibacterial activity was determined by tube dilution method against two bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* (gram +ve) and *Escherichia coli* (gram -ve). The most active among the series were 2-chloro- and 4-chloro-12H-[1]-benzopyrano[3,4-b][1,4]benzothiazin-6-ones which showed no growth at 10 ppm against *E. coli*, whereas unsubstituted, 2-chloro-, 4-chloro-

and 2,4-dichloro-compounds were active against both the bacteria at 100 ppm only.

For antifungal activity, plate method was employed against two fungi, namely *Aspergillus niger* Vontieghan and *Alternaria alternata* (Ff) Keissler. 2-Chloro-12*H*-[1]-benzopyrano[3,4-*b*][1,4]benzothiazin-6-one exhibited 100% inhibition only at 100 ppm. 2-Bromo- and 4-chloro- derivatives inhibited 60% growth of both the fungi at 100 ppm only.

The results of testing clearly indicate that the halogen substitution steps up the activity.

Experimental

General procedure : 7-Methyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (2.8 g) and 2-aminothiophenol (1.25 ml) were dissolved in dry dimethyl sulphoxide (8 ml). The solution was stirred and heated on a hot plate at 150° for 3 h. On cooling, red crystals formed were filtered and recrystallised from excess of hot methanol.

Above compound was treated with acetic anhydride and a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid and worked out by usual procedure to get the acetate.

Raney nickel desulphurisation : 7-Methyl-12*H*-[1]-benzopyrano[3,4-*b*][1,4]benzothiazin-6-one (1 g) was dissolved in ethanol (50 ml) and the resulting solution was refluxed on water-bath for a while. Raney nickel (0.5 g) was added portionwise, refluxing was continued for 5 h. The colourless solution was filtered and the excess ethanol was distilled off. The colourless compound, 7-methyl-4-anilincoumarin was filtered and recrystallised from hot ethanol, m.p. 244°.

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